

The Study on Comparison of Some Landraces and Hybrid Tomatoes in Myanmar

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Abstract

The morphological identification of nine tomato plants, are seven landraces and two hybrids belonging to the family solanaceae. The seven landraces names of tomato cultivars were Waiegyi, Nyopin, Sakyin, Kyauk Pa Daung, Htone Pho, Falam and Tha Yet Taw Varieties. Two Hybrid names are Hybrid Nirvana and Hybrid 701. These tomato plants have been undertaken in Department of Plant Breeding, Physiology and Ecology of Yazin Agriculture University. This study was done from August to December in the year 2016. According to the results of the study local seven plants and two hybrid plants had some different morphological characters. In this paper, the photographic plants showing their respective natural habits inflorescences, flowers, fruit shape and size, longitudinal section of flowers and transverse section of fruit of each plant were presented.

keyword: Landraces, Hybrid, Nirvana, Hybrid 701

Introduction

Tomato is one of the most valuable and popular vegetables worldwide (Amini and Ehsanpour, 2005). It belongs to the nightshade family, Solanaceae. Its scientific name is *Solanum lycopersicum* (L.) and is also called *Lycopersicon lycopersicum* (L.) H. Karst. *Solanum* is the largest genus in the Solanaceae and one of the largest genera of flowering plants.

Tomatoes and tomato-based products are an important agricultural commodity worldwide. More than 80% of tomatoes grown worldwide are processed into products such as tomato juice, paste, puree, catsup, sauce, and salsa. Tomato fruit is rich in organic acids, sugars, dietary fibre, pectic substances, proteins, fats, minerals (potassium, phosphorus, sulphur, magnesium, calcium, iron, copper, and sodium), vitamins, and carotenoids possessing antioxidant qualities (lycopene, β -carotene, etc.).

Landraces are an important cultural and economic heritage of agriculture. They have a low but stable yield and a great deal of adaptation against biotic and abiotic factors. Although due to their favorable characteristics (disease tolerance, rich taste, good fruit content and a great variability in color and shape) there is a high chance that tomato landraces can earn a place for themselves, especially in the organic farming.

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Materials and Methods

- This study was conducted at the Department of Plant Breeding, Physiology and Ecology, University of Agricultural, Yezin

- Landrace tomato varieties – collected and grown on the seed bed

- 2 weeks old Seedlings were transplanted small plastic bags

- The seedling from small plastic bags were transplanted to bigger ones.
- Supporting stem were made with bamboo
- Taxonomic characters were studied

Results

Hybrid Nirvana

Annual herbs, about 150-175 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate, with 9 leaflets on petioles. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 7-9 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 2 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (6), synsepalous, campanulate persistent and often much enlarge in fruit, petals (6), yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpel 1, bilocular, many ovules on prominently peltate placentas, Fruits, berry, ovate-oblong, 3.0-5.0 cm long red, thick mesocarp. Seeds 0.1-0.3 cm long, ovate-oblong.

Hybrid 701

Annual herbs, about 150-175 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate, with 9 leaflets on petioles. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 5-6 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 2 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (5), synsepalous, persistent and often much enlarged in fruit; petals (5), yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpel 1, bilocular, many ovules on peltate placentas. Fruits berry, ovate-oblong, 3.0-5.0 cm long, red, thickmesocarp. Seeds about 0.1-0.3cm long, ovate-oblong.

Landrace - Waiegyi Variety

Annual herbs, about 150-175 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate, with 9 leaflets on petioles. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 3-5 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 1.8 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (5), persistent and often much enlarged in fruit; petals (5), yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpel 1, bilocular, many ovules on peltate placentas. Fruits oblong, berry, 3.5-5.0 cm long red, thick mesocarp. Seeds 0.1-0.3 cm long, oblong.

Landrace-Nyopin Variety

Annual herbs, about 160-175 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate, with 9 leaflets on petioles. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 5-7 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 1.8cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (5), synsepalous, campanulate, persistent and often much enlarged in fruit, inferior. Petals (5), yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpel 1, bilocular, many ovules on peltate placentas. Fruits sub-globose, berry, 3.0-4.0 cm long red, thick mesocarp.

Landrace-Sakyin Variety

Annual herbs, about 145-170 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 5 folwers per inflorescences. Flower about 2 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (5), synsepalous, persistent and often much enlarged in fruit, petals (5), yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpels 1, three locules placentation axile, many ovules on prominently peltate placentas. Fruits berry, globose, 3.0-5.0 cm long red, thin mesocarp. Seeds 0.1-0.3 cm long, ovate-oblong.

Landrace-Kyuak Pa Daung Variety

Annual herbs, about 145-170 cm high. Leaves ovate-lanceolate. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 5 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 2 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals 5, persistent and often much enlarged in fruit, inferior. petals 5, yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpels 1, three locules many ovules on peltate placentas. Fruits berry, globose, 4.0-5.0 cm long. Seeds 0.1-0.2 cm long, ovate-oblong.

Landrace-Htone Pho (Wild) variety

Annual herbs, about 140-165 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 5-8 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 2 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (5), synsepalous, persistent and often much enlarged in fruit, inferior, petals (5), yellow, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpels 1, bilocular, many ovules on peltate placentas. Fruits berry, globose, about 2 cm long. Seeds 0.1-0.2 cm long, ovate-oblong.

Landrace-Falam variety

Annual herbs, about 165-170 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate. Inflorescences terminal or lateral cyme, 7 flowers per inflorescences. Flower about 1.7 cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (5), persistent and often much enlarged in fruit, inferior; petals (5), lobe oblong, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpels 1, bilocular, many ovules on peltate placentas. Fruits berry, subglobose, 2.0-2.5cm long and wide, red. Seeds 0.1-0.2 cm long, ovate.

Landrace - Tha Yet Taw variety

Annual herbs, about 170-175 cm high, Leaves ovate-lanceolate. Inflorescence terminal or lateral cyme, 6-9 flowers per inflorescences. Flowers about 2cm long and wide, yellow, sepals (8), persistent and often much enlarged in fruit, inferior; petals (8), lobes oblong, reflexed. Stamens 5, epipetalous, anther fuse to form columns around the pistil. Carpel 1, 5 locules, many ovules on prominently peltate placentas, Fruits globose, 8-10cm long. Seeds 0.1-0.3cm long.

Morphology and Taxonomic characters of Hybrid – Nirvana

The whole plants

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruit and T.S. of fruit

Fig. 1. Hybrid- Nirvana

The whole plants

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruit and T.S. of fruit

Fig. 2. Hybrid-701

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Ripe fruit and TS of fruit

Fig. 3. Waiwgyi Variety

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruit cluster, fruits and TS of fruit

Fig. 4. Nyo Pin Variety

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruits and TS of fruit

Fig. 5. Sakyin Variety

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruits and TS of fruit

Fig. 6. Kyuank Pa Daung Variety

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruits and TS of fruit

Fig. 7. Htone Pho Variety

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruits and TS of fruit

Fig. 8. Falam Variety

The whole plant

Two weeks old seedling

Flower and L.S of flower

Fruit and TS of fruits

Fig. 9. Tha Yet Taw Variety

Fig. 10. Comparism of Flowers and L.S of Flowers

Fig. 11. Comparism of fruits shape and size

Fig. 12. Comparism of T.S of Fruits

Discussion and Conclusion

The fruit size and shape of tested landrace varieties and hybrid are quite different. Moreover the fruit locules are quite different. Some has two locules, some are three locules and one landrace variety has many locules per fruit. The size of flower and the number of sepals and petals are also quite different. Some varieties have 5 sepals and petals, some have 6 like in hybrids and some had more than 6 e.g. Tha Yet Taw landrace variety. This variety possess bigger flower size than others. In tomato as well as in other crops, size of the fruit is the key factor determining yield. This is why mechanisms of regulation fruit growth and development were the research topic for many authors (Bussieres, 1995; Andrews *et al.*, 2002).

Crop yield is the result of many morphophysiological and biochemical processes depending on environmental factors and genetical background (Kulkarni and Deshpande, 2006). Landraces are an important cultural and economic heritage of agriculture. They have a low but stable yield and a great deal of adaptation against biotic and abiotic factors. Although due to their favourable characteristics (disease tolerance, rich taste, good fruit content and a great variability in color and shape) there is a high chance that tomato landraces can earn a place for themselves, especially in the organic farming. The fruit is rich in lycopene which many have beneficial health effects. There effect was highest for cancer diseases.

According to this study, landrace tomatoes are different from plant types, leaves' shape, flower cluster, flower's shape and size, fruit shape and size and locules per fruit. These landrace varieties are very important for other breeding program.

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